

Biology of Leaf Eating Caterpillar *Noorda blitealis* Wlk. On *Moringa oleifera* Lam

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Abstract

Moringa oleifera Lam. is widely grown in Sri Lanka. In recent years, a seasonal pest *Noorda blitealis* Wlk. turned into a major pest on Periyakulam 1 (PKM 1) annual *Moringa* in Jaffna district. A study was carried out to record the biological and morphological characters of *N. blitealis* on PKM1 *Moringa* under Sri Lankan climatic condition. Larvae were collected from the affected areas and reared in the laboratory. *N. blitealis* females laid oval and creamy eggs in clusters which had an incubation period of 2.2 ± 0.4 days with 80.4% of hatchability. The larvae were transparent to creamy, light green and became pink at the final stage with a body length of 2-20 mm. Five instars were determined using Dyar's rule. At the each moult, the mean growth ratio of head capsule width was 1.54. The larval period was 9 to 11 days. The period of first, second, third, fourth and fifth instar was 1.3 ± 0.1 , 2.0 ± 0.6 , 2.1 ± 0.5 , 2.45 ± 0.6 and 2.2 ± 0.4 days, respectively. The obtect pupa was dark brown, 8.4 ± 0.5 mm long and the mean pupal period was 7 ± 0.92 days. The adult emergence was $67.79 \pm 5.33\%$. Moths were small with dark brown abdomen. The female and male adult longevity were 10.35 ± 2.08 and 7.11 ± 2.85 days, respectively. The male: female sex ratio was 1: 1.3.

Keywords: *Noorda blitealis*, *Moringa oleifera*, Dyar's rule

Introduction

The multipurpose tree, *Moringa oleifera* Lam. (Moringaceae) is distributed in various tropical and subtropical countries [1]. The tree has high medicinal and nutritional values. Several parts of the plant contain a wide range of minerals and are a good source of proteins, vitamins, β -carotene, amino acids, and phenolics [2]. In Sri Lanka, *Moringa* is grown in the dry and intermediate zones in commercial fields and home gardens mainly for pods and leaves. The soil and climatic conditions in Jaffna favour *Moringa* cultivation. Annual *Moringa*; Periyakulam 1 (PKM1) and Jaffna local are cultivated under irrigated and rain fed system in Jaffna district.

Seasonal pests have been a major limitation in *Moringa* cultivation. In the past few years, the PKM1 *Moringa* crops were severely attacked by a leaf-eating caterpillar *Noorda blitealis* Wlk. The moth belongs to the Family Pyralidae. It is one of the major pests in *Moringa* cultivation which damages the *Moringa* leaves. Webbed, skeletonised and dried leaves are common symptoms of the pest. In severe condition, complete defoliation occurs, leading to plant death [3]. *N. blitealis* feeds on *Moringa stenopetala* Baker (Cufod.) and *Moringa oleifera* Lam. [3,4]. Since *N. blitealis* is a newly emerging pest in the region, there is limited information available on the leaf-eating caterpillar on annual PKM1 *Moringa* under Sri Lankan conditions. Hence, the biology and morphological characters of *N. blitealis* were studied in the laboratory.

Material and methods

The larvae of *N. blitealis* were collected from the leaves, shoots, and stems of PKM1 *Moringa oleifera* at Sempianpattu and Nallur in Jaffna district of Sri Lanka from November 2014 to May 2015. They were reared in plastic rearing chambers at $27 \pm 1.7^\circ\text{C}$ and $78 \pm 6.1\%$ relative humidity in the laboratory at Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jaffna. The larvae were fed with fresh PKM 1 *Moringa* leaves for every 6 hours. The size, colour, number of instars and the larval period were reordered through careful observation. The instars were determined from 514 healthy selected larvae. The head capsule width was measured using a calibrated ocular micrometer to determine the instars according to Dyar's rule [5]. In order to restrict the movement of the larvae, they were kept at 4°C temperature for 2 min before measuring the head capsule width. To include all the instars in the sample, the larvae were collected periodically to ensure that the population of larvae had all the instars. The final instar larvae were transferred to rearing chambers having

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1.5 cm thick sterilized sandy soils at the bottom to facilitate the pupation. Pupal period, length of the pupae, and colour were recorded using 92 pupae.

After pupation, the newly emerged moths were reared in rearing chambers providing fresh *Moringa* leaves and 10% honey soaked in cotton wool. A total number of 92 moths of both sexes were used to count their adult longevity. The adults were dissected to differentiate male and female moths. Both male and female morphological characters were studied

Results and discussion

Females laid eggs in clusters on the ventral surface of the leaves. The eggs were oval in shape and white to creamy in colour. The incubation period of the egg on PKM 1 annual *Moringa* was 2.2 ± 0.4 days with 80.4% of egg hatchability.

The eggs hatched into larvae which were creamy to transparent in colour. In following instars, the larvae were light green to creamy, and in the final instar the colour changed into pink. White to creamy hairs were found on the larval body. The head capsule of the larva was light brown in colour. The size of the larvae of all instars was between 2-20 mm. In the last instar, the feeding and movement of the larva were slowed down.

The larval instars were confirmed by measuring the head capsule width of the larvae and applying Dyar's rule. The head capsule widths obtained from 514 larvae was plotted against the number of larvae. The histogram (Figure 1) was produced by different groups of larvae. At the each moult of larval development, the head capsule width increased with an average ratio of 1.54 (Table 1).

Five different groups were obtained in the experiment. The first group included the neonate larvae which were newly hatched from the eggs. The fifth group included the larvae, which subsequently pupated without showing any further moulting. The larvae belonging to this group was considered to represent the fifth instar. The sclerotized structure of an insect is assumed to remain constant in size during an instar [6]. According to Dyar's rule the logarithms of the measurement of the larval head capsule width of different instars show a strong linear line while plotting against the number of instars. The deviations from the straight line indicate the missing instars in the sample. In figure 2, a straight line was obtained without any deviation which indicates that there were no missing instars. Pearson's correlation between the mean capsule widths and the larval instars was $r^2 = 0.937$.

The larval period ranged from 9 to 11 days. Out of 130 larvae subjected to the experiment at the mean instar periods of the first, second, third, fourth and fifth instars were 1.3 ± 0.1 , 2.0 ± 0.6 , 2.1 ± 0.5 , 2.45 ± 0.6 and 2.2 ± 0.4 days, respectively. Information on the number of the larval instars and the biological cycle of the insect helps to understand the population dynamics and management of the pest [7,8].

The insect pupated in the soil, making a pale colour pupal case. The pupa was obiect type and dark brown in colour. The mean length of the pupa was 8.4 ± 0.5 mm. The mean pupal period was 7.07 ± 0.92 days. The mean adult emergence percentage was $67.79 \pm 5.33\%$. Adult emerged as moths, and their abdomen was dark brown, palpi were longer than the width of the head, the forewings were dark brown with white patches and had a dark brown band at the posterior margin with brown fringes of hair. The hind wings were white and hyalinised. The hind wings had a dark brown wide band at the posterior margin with light brown fringes of hair. The male: female sex ratio was 1: 1.3. The adult longevity of female was 10.35 ± 2.08 days, and male adult longevity was 7.11 ± 2.85 days. The adult longevity of females was higher than males. The morphological and biological characters of *N.blitealis* were more or less similar to the studies done in India and Sudan. [3,9,10]. Selvi and Muthukrishnan reported that the biological attributes of *N.blitealis* vary to different annual *Moringa* accessions [9]. The relative intake of protein and energy source has significant impact on an individual's growth, development, survival, and fecundity [11,12].

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Fig 1. The measurement of larval capsule width plotted against the number of larvae producing five different groups.

Fig 2. Relationship between the log of head capsule width and the corresponding larval instar of *N. blitealis*.

Table 1. The average width of larval head capsule of *N. blitealis* and growth rate during the larval development

Instar	Number of larvae	Width of head capsule mean (mm) ± SD	Variation of coefficient (VC)	Growth rate
1 st	84	0.23 ± 0.02	0.08	1.78
2 nd	70	0.41 ± 0.04	0.09	1.53
3 rd	103	0.63 ± 0.05	0.07	1.34
4 th	127	0.85 ± 0.06	0.07	1.51
5 th	130	1.29 ± 0.06	0.04	–
Mean growth rate				1.54

Figure 3: Life stages of *N. blitealis* Wlk.

(a), (b), (c) larval stages, (d) final instar larva (e) Pupa (f) Adults

Conclusion

The present study reports the biological and morphological features of *N. blitealis* on PKM1 *Moringa* in Sri Lanka. Knowledge of biological and morphological characters of the pest is necessary to identify the pest in early stages of infestation and subsequently help in taking effective control measures to manage *N. blitealis* in Jaffna district.

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